

Questionnaire for apprentices

Year of training: 1 2 3 4 Sex: f m Matura: planned no

Apprenticeship as: _____ First language: _____

Part 1: Informal computer usage

1) Which of the following devices do you have access to?

- | | belongs to me | at home | different location |
|---|--|-----------------------|--------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Smartphone | yes <input type="radio"/> no <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Tablet | yes <input type="radio"/> no <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Computer with Internet access | yes <input type="radio"/> no <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Computer without Internet access | yes <input type="radio"/> no <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | _____ |

2) For how many hours do you use your computer, tablet or smartphone on working days?

- not at all less than 1/2 hour 1/2 to 1 hour 1-2 h 2-3 h 3-4 h more than 4 h

3) For how many hours a day do you use your computer, tablet or smartphone at weekends?

- not at all less than 1/2 hour 1/2 to 1 hour 1-2 h 2-3 h 3-4 h more than 4 h

4) To what hour at night do you use your computer, tablet or smartphone on working days?

- not at all until I fall asleep until _____ o'clock

5) To what hour at night do you use your computer, tablet or smartphone at weekends?

- not at all until I fall asleep until _____ o'clock

6) Do you use your mobile phone at work?

- always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

7) Do you use your mobile phone during apprenticeship trainings?

- always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

8) Do you use your mobile phone at vocational school?

- always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

9) Do you use one of these devices to listen to music?

- Computer Tablet Smartphone none

10) Do you use one of these devices to play games?

- Computer Tablet Smartphone none

11) Do you use one of these devices to watch films?

- Computer Tablet Smartphone none

12) Do you use one of these devices to look at photographs?

- Computer Tablet Smartphone none

13) Do you use one of these devices to access social media sites (e.g. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter...)?

- Computer Tablet Smartphone none

14) How often do you surf the Internet just like that, without a specific goal?

- always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

15) Do you use the Internet for work? (e.g. gathering information, emails ...)

- always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

16) Do you use the Internet for vocational school? (e.g. studying, preparing presentations ...)
 always very frequently occasionally rarely very rarely never

17) Which of these applications do you use?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Facebook | <input type="checkbox"/> Email |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Twitter | <input type="checkbox"/> Skype |
| <input type="checkbox"/> What's App / messenger / iMessage | <input type="checkbox"/> Snapchat |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Instagram | <input type="checkbox"/> YouTube |
| <input type="checkbox"/> others: _____ | <input type="checkbox"/> others: _____ |

18) What are the activities you mainly use your computer, tablet or smartphone for?

Part 2: Self-evaluation

19) I can take a picture or record a video and upload it to a website.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

20) I am good with computers, tablets or smartphones.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

21) When I encounter a problem while working with a computer, tablet, or smartphone, I know who I can turn to and I ask for help.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

22) When I encounter a problem while working with a computer, tablet, or smartphone, I give up and stop what I was doing.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

23) When I encounter a problem while working with a computer, tablet, or smartphone, I try to solve the problem on my own, even if it is difficult for me.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

24) I like working with computers, tablets and smartphones.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

25) I could use a new online platform for my vocational training if I had never used one like this before.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

26) I could use a new online platform for my vocational training if there is no one around to tell me what to do as I go.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

27) I could use a new online platform for my vocational training if I had only the manuals for reference.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

28) I could use a new online platform for my vocational training if I could call someone for help if I got stuck.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree

29) I could use a new online platform for my vocational training if I had seen someone else use it before trying myself.
 completely agree mostly agree mostly disagree completely disagree